

ISic0417

I.Sicily inscription 0417

Language

Latin

Type

building; honorific

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

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Jonathan Prag

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Autopsy

2014.09.10

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

in the area of the Great altar of Hieron II

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 252

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [---]CAE[---]

2. [---][---]

Apparatus

Text of CIL

The letter is either 'i' or 'l'.

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491646

EDCS 21900480

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7137 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/item/buchseite/650768>)

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